

PHOTO-REACTION BETWEEN IODINE AND SALTS OF CARBOXYLIC ACIDS IN PRESENCE OF METAL IONS AS CATALYSTS

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Photo-reaction between aqueous solutions of salts of hydroxy-carboxylic acids and iodine at appreciable rates takes place only in the presence of traces of certain metallic salts. An essential feature of these reactions is the formation of complex anions containing the metal. The kinetics, measured by the rate of disappearance of free iodine in the system, is the net result of a series of complicated simultaneous reactions, an outline of which is given.

The results indicate the existence in aqueous solution of a number of co-ordination complex salts of metals with hydroxy-carboxylic acids under conditions which require further investigation.

The experimental work, the results of which are summarised in this paper, was undertaken in an attempt to find out whether the salts of any of the other simple carboxylic acids react with I_2 in a manner capable of kinetic measurement, like the well known $K_2C_2O_4 - I_2$ photo-reaction. In spite of some claims to the contrary (Mukherjee and Dhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 32, 1308; 1929, 33, 850) it soon became evident that when the reagents were carefully purified there was no appreciable reaction between I_2 (in the presence of KI) and the sodium salts of the following carboxylic acids at temperatures upto 40° :

Acetic, propionic, butyric, succinic, maleic, benzoic, phthalic, glycollic, malic, tartaric, citric, mandelic and glyceric.

On the other hand, we have found that addition of traces of the following salts immediately promotes reaction with hydroxy-carboxylic acids in light :

Manganese, chromium, iron, cobalt, uranyl salts and cerium; nickel being a notable exception. Carboxylic acids containing no OH groups do not react with I_2 in light in the presence of added catalysts, with the exception of Mn^{2+} , which is oxidised to insoluble H_2MnO_3 .

It has been observed that at temperatures between 30° and 40° all these reactions proceed with negligibly slow velocity both in the light (using a 1000 watt lamp as source) and in the dark if the reactants used are pure and precautions are taken to prevent loss of I_2 by evaporation.

The most effective photo-catalysts were found to be Mn^{2+} and Cr^{3+} . The concentration of catalysts employed varied from 0.091 milliatom of the metal ion to 3.64 milliatom per litre (*i. e.* about 1 to 40 milliatoms of the catalysts in the presence of 50 mM of I_2 and 1000 mM of Na-salt) and at these concentrations the reactions are rapidly accelerated in light, the effect being roughly proportional to the concentration of catalyst. In the dark, the reactions are extremely slow. In the presence of Fe^{3+} , $(UO_2)^{2+}$, Co^{3+} and Ce^{4+} the reaction rates were considerably slower in the light of a 1000 watt lamp, but still very rapid in sunlight. The curves for the relative rates of reaction were all of the same type, so only one set is reproduced by way of illustration, that of sodium malate and iodine.

Although some attempts have appeared in the literature, it does not seem possible to draw any useful conclusions concerning the kinetics of the reactions

from a study of these curves. The factors which influence the reaction rates are many; thus increase of $[\text{H}^+]$ ultimately suppresses it, whereas withdrawal of I_2 in the equilibrium:

as the amount of I^- present progressively increases in the course of the reaction, renders kinetic interpretation impossible. Moreover, it has been found that in some systems solid iodination products appear, which effectively rules out photochemical measurement for the purposes of determining the order of reaction, quantum yield etc. Other complications will be referred to later. The curves obtained show the relative effectiveness of the added metal ions in promoting reaction, the nature of which can be further studied by examining the reaction products. A summary of the results so far obtained is shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Sodium salts.	Catalytic activity of the metal ions (3.64 milliatoms per litre).	Products of photo-reaction with I ₂ using the catalysts mentioned.	Products of photo-reaction with FeCl ₃ .	Products of reaction with chromic acid.
Citrate	Mn > Cr > Ce > (UO ₂) > Co > Fe	(Mn, Cr, Ce, Fe) tetra- & hexa-iodoacetones and acetone.	Acetone dicarboxylic acid and acetone.	Acetone dicarboxylic acid and Acetone.
Tartrate	Mn > Cr > Co > Fe > (UO ₂)	(Mn, Cr, Co, Fe) glyoxal-carbonic acid and glyoxal.	Glyoxal-carbonic acid & very small quantities of glyoxal (in light). In dark these products have not been detected.	...
Malate	Mn > Cr > Co > (UO ₂) > Ce > Fe	(Mn, Cr, Co, Fe) small quantities of iodoform.	Acetaldehyde & a product giving hydrazone with 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (not yet identified).	...
Mandelate	Cr > Mn > Fe > (UO ₂) > Ce	(Mn, Fe) benzaldehyde; (Cr) benzaldehyde & phenylglyoxalic acid.	Benzaldehyde.	Benzaldehyde & phenylglyoxalic acid.
Lactate	Cr > Mn > Fe > Co > (UO ₂) > Ce	(Mn) acetaldehyde; (Cr) pyruvic acid & small quantities of iodoform; (Fe) small quantities of iodoform.	Acetaldehyde.	Acetic acid.
Glycolate	Mn > Cr > Co > Fe	(Mn, Cr) formaldehyde.	...	Formaldehyde.
Glycerate	Cr > Mn > Fe > Co	(Mn, Cr) glyoxal.	...	...

The relative order of effectiveness of the various metal catalysts is unaffected by changes of concentration of reactants, changes in temperature, changes in p_H , or nature of the cation. The end-products, which were identified by the usual methods, are in all cases simple oxidation products or iodination compounds derived from these. There is a general similarity between the results obtained with different catalysts, with a few exceptions, indicating a similar reaction-mechanism irrespective of the catalyst employed.

The end solutions, after the free I_2 had been used up photochemically, were usually found to contain the metal in a higher state of valency than that originally employed. They were with few exceptions photochemically sensitive, disappearing with a measurable velocity, rapidly in light, slowly in the dark. Identification of a higher valency state in the case of manganese for example was shown as follows:—

The end solutions, no longer containing free I_2 , are brown in colour, dialysable (absence of colloidal complexes) and become colourless when further exposed to light (reduction to Mn^{II} condition).

The brown solutions (i) give the pink colouration of potassium manganioxalate when treated with $K_2C_2O_4$, (ii) start the 'Eder' reaction with $K_2C_2O_4$ and $HgCl_2$ under N_2 in the dark, (iii) liberate I_2 from KI ; all indicating the presence of tervalent Mn in a comparatively stable form, i.e., as a complex, since simple Mn^{III} salts decompose immediately in aqueous solution and are also instantly reduced by I^- .

Iron Complexes.—Among the acids mentioned above, formation of iron complexes was found to be restricted only to those containing OH groups. The best known of these are the tartrates, the formation of two types of which, identified by Franke (*Annalen*, 1931, 486, 242) may be written

containing 4-co-ordinate and 6-co-ordinate tervalent Fe respectively. The presence of an acid group like OH is necessary to take up one of the co-ordinate positions in the anion. As already stated, only hydroxy-carboxylic acids have been found to react with I_2 in the presence of metal catalysts; the formation of complex anions is thus an essential link in these reactions.

The effect of light on systems containing (I) and (II) (which are stable in the dark) may be summarised as follows:

The deep citron-yellow solution of sodium tartrate and ferric chloride in equimolecular proportions (I), containing free ferri-tartaric acid, is highly photosensitive. The acid decomposes rapidly in sunlight leaving a solution containing the whole of the iron in the ferrous state, together with glyoxalcarboxylic acid and small amounts of glyoxal. Neutralisation of the H by addition of $NaOH$ pro-

portionately reduces the light sensitivity. In the presence of 3 mol s. of NaOH (II) a reddish brown solution is obtained which is completely stable both in the light and in the dark.

All other hydroxycarboxylates tabulated above gave the same citron-yellow solutions in the anionic complex form with Fe^{+++} , decomposable photochemically, giving the products shown in column 4 of Table I.

The effect of increasing the concentration of H^+ is to decompose these complexes. In systems such as those employed in our original experiments with I_2 , the initial buffer action of large excess of sodium tartrate nullifies the effect of the H^+ , so that we have at first conditions favourable for the production of the equilibrium in (II). The oxidation products in column 3 are practically identical with those shown in column 4. It may be noted that Benrath (*Annalen*, 1911, 382, 222; *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1917, 204, 190) obtained similar products by the action of ferric salts on the free acids in sunlight. Ciamician and Silber (*Ber.*, 1913, 46, 1558; 1914, 47, 640) also obtained almost the same results (explained as being due to autoxidation) by exposing these acids for prolonged periods to sunlight in sealed bulbs containing air or oxygen. It seems highly probable that Ciamician and Silber's results (*loc. cit.*) were not due to autoxidation, but to the presence in solution of traces of iron, which are removable only with great difficulty.

It appears from the above that the photo-reaction is not due to self-reduction of the complex ion, as stated by Franke, but to the action of the pseudo-acid on the free tartaric acid. An overall equation might be written for example

with dehydrogenation of the tartaric acid and formation of simple oxidation products. This type of reaction has been experimentally confirmed by exposing crystals of ferritartaric acid to sunlight in presence $M/10$ tartaric acid when the above reaction took place rapidly. There was no reaction in absence of free tartaric acid.

Manganese Complexes.—Manganic "alum" $\text{Mn}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$, K_2SO_4 , prepared by the method of Meyer and Best (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1899, 22, 169) when added to solutions of sodium salts of various hydroxy-carboxylic acids, so as to contain 3.64 milliatom Mn^{+++} per litre (*i.e.*, in the same concentration as in the experiments with I_2) contained the Mn^{+++} in the form of a complex. This was shown by the fact that in some cases, particularly that of citrate, no iodine was liberated from KI, and in other cases slowly, whereas the original manganese alum instantly did so. Moreover, the latter rapidly hydrolysed to black insoluble H_2MnO_3 in presence of water, but no immediate hydrolysis took place in the presence of concentrated solutions of salts of hydroxy-carboxylic acids. All the solutions except citrate decomposed photochemically giving the products shown in Table I, column 5. With citrate there was a very slow thermal reduction, not accelerated by light. The rest were all stable in the dark over several days.

In the presence of KI it was found that I_2 was liberated at variable measurable rates in the dark; fastest with mandelate and lactate; immeasurably slowly with citrate. Systems containing the latter gave no test for free I_2 under any of the following conditions:—

(i) Immediately after the addition of manganic alum, (ii) after highly diluting the mixture, (iii) after standing 24 hours in the dark, and (iv) after exposure to sunlight. On the other hand, if I_2 was added it was slowly used up in the dark.

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

The relative rates at which the I_2 was liberated from these solutions is shown in Fig. 2. The slow and variable rates of reaction with KI explain the function of the complexes; without their presence the metal in the higher state of valency would immediately be reduced by I^- present and thus no oxidation of the hydroxy-carboxylic acid would ensue.

Fig. 2 may be interpreted as follows, taking a dibasic acid as an example,

These relative rates of reaction with KI are therefore a measure of the rate of liberation of Mn^{+++} from the pseudo-acid in equilibrium (a) and the relative stability of the complex ions, since reduction of free Mn^{+++} by I^- is instantaneous.

In Fig. 3 are shown the relative rates of reduction when solutions containing manganic "alum" (3.64 milliatom of Mn^{+++} per litre) and $M/4$ sodium carboxylates are exposed to the light source. The course of reaction was measured by taking out from time to time a quantity of the mixture and adding it to a solution of KI acidified with HCl to destroy the complex. The amount of I_2 liberated gave a measure of the total Mn^{+++} present in the system at any time. Compared with Fig. 2 it is seen that citrate solutions, which contain no free Mn^{+++} , are photochemically stable, whereas lactate systems, which contain the largest relative concentration of available Mn^{+++} , are reduced photochemically at the fastest rate (Tartrate has been found to give different oxidation products in the light and in the dark; a further detailed study of this reaction is in progress).

From these results, however, it seems permissible to infer that (i) the complex anions are stable both in the light and in the dark, (ii) the pseudo-acid is a powerful thermal oxidising agent, the action of which may or may not be subject to photochemical acceleration, (iii) photochemical oxidation results from interaction between free Mn^{+++} and the free carboxylic acid.

In our original experiments, since free Mn^{+++} cannot exist in the presence of KI, the rate-determining reaction must be the oxidation of the free carboxylic acid by the pseudo-acid complex; and only those conditions which favour the maximum concentration of the latter will produce the maximum catalytic effects. So long as free I_2 is present we have the photo-process

taking place, so that reduced Mn^{++} in (b) is instantly returned to the appropriate complex trivalent form.

The above mechanism has been proved in the case of citrate systems by starting with mixtures of sodium citrate, manganic alum and I_2 in the dark and gradually increasing $[H^+]$ by addition of free citric acid; there is found an optimum $[H^+]$ corresponding to the maximum of pseudo-acid in equilibrium, at which tetraiodoacetone is formed at the maximum rate.

Relative Apparent Catalytic Efficiency of Iron and Manganese.—In Table I it will be observed that Mn^{++} is a much more efficient catalyst than Fe^{+++} , especially so in the case of citrate and malate. The difference between them resides in the fact that whereas the oxidation of free hydroxy-carboxylic acid by the ferri-acid is weakly photochemical with intensity of illumination experimentally employed, in the case of the mangani-acid there is more powerful thermal reaction.

This has been shown by taking two solutions containing equal concentration of sodium hydroxycarboxylate and free carboxylic acids with equivalent concentrations of Mn^{+++} and Fe^{+++} respectively and exposing them to the same light intensity. The total concentration of the metallic ions was measured from time to time and it was seen that the Mn^{+++} was reduced much more rapidly than Fe^{+++} under similar conditions. There is evidence, however, that the position of iron in the series (Table I, column 2) may be altered by varying the intensity of the incident light.

Although it has not been possible to carry out similar experiments with other metals, it is to be inferred from the above that the order of apparent catalytic activity of the ions, enumerated in Table I, is determined largely by the rate of reaction between the free complex acid and the free hydroxy-carboxylic acids.

Complexes of other metals.—The results obtained by adding chromic acid in equivalent quantity to the same concentrations of hydroxy-carboxylic acids is shown in Table I, column 6. The similarity in general behaviour to iron and manganese shows that here also corresponding complexes are formed, but it has not been possible so far to determine to what state of valency the Cr ⁺⁺⁺ ions, employed in our original experiments, has been raised, and what is the exact nature of the complexes formed with cobalt, cerium and uranium, the existence of hitherto unknown complexes containing these metals in a higher state of valency is also indicated.

Iodination products.—The iodination products formed from citrate, hexa- and tetraiodoacetone, and from malate and lactate, iodoform (Table I, column 3), are due to reaction between free I₂ and primary oxidation products of these acids; in the case of citrate, acetone dicarboxylic acid; lactate, pyruvic acid; and malate, probably an isomer of pyruvic acid.

We have observed that free I₂ slowly disappears when added to solutions of sodium citrate and manganic alum in the dark, evidently by reaction with acetone dicarboxylic acid which is being formed. This explains the so-called photochemical "after-effect" in the sodium citrate-iodine reaction to which attention was called by Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 277).

CONCLUSIONS

1. The general reaction-mechanism may be represented in the manner already given under manganese complexes (*vide supra*). The I₂ dissociates photochemically producing the metal in a higher state of valency. The metal ions thus produced may react *photochemically* with the free hydroxy-carboxylic acid giving simple oxidation products; the same products may also be obtained by *thermal* or *photochemical* reaction between the pseudo complex acid and the free hydroxy-carboxylic acid. The relationship between these two processes, which appears to be specific to each system, is the subject of further investigation.

2. A side reaction may take place between a metal ion M⁺⁺⁺ and KI present in the solution, tending to set up another state

The rate of the forward reaction differs with different metals. The effect of the anionic metallic complex is to prevent this reaction occurring to any appreciable extent and to conserve the higher valency state of the metal in equation (a) (p. 266).

3. Inhibition of the reaction by increase in concentration of I' is explained by shift of equilibrium in (ii) to the right, also by withdrawal of free I_2 in the equilibrium $I_2 + I' \rightleftharpoons I_3'$; inhibition through increase of $[H^+]$ by shift of equilibrium in eqn. (a) (p. 266) to the left.

4. The kinetics of the apparent catalytic reaction and the order of comparative efficiency of the various metals employed, as measured by the rate of disappearance of I_2 , is thus the net result of a number of simultaneous reactions of variable rates in (a, b, c, p. 268) and (ii). It has not been found possible so far to give quantitative expression to the latter, so as to be able to predict the comparative catalytic efficiency of the metal ions with the light intensity applied.

5. The general similarity in the experimental course of the reaction with all the metals employed indicates the existence of a number of co-ordination complex salts of hydroxy-carboxylic acids and manganese, chromium, cerium, cobalt and uranium, raised to at least a trivalent state, which have not yet been described.

It may be noted in conclusion that attempts which have appeared in the literature to study these reactions in the absence of KI *i.e.*, using I_2 in aqueous solution to commence with, apart from difficulties of measurement, do not appear to simplify the kinetics, since reaction, if it happens at all, is accompanied by the simultaneous production of I' .

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VELOCITY OF TRANSFORMATION OF 1 : 3 : 5 TRIKETONES INTO 2 : 6-DISUBSTITUTED γ -PYRONES. PART II

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Velocity of transformation of 1 : 3 : 5-triketones into γ -pyrones has been investigated and is found to be unimolecular like the standard substance, acetone dioxalic ester. It is therefore concluded that diacetylacetone and its homologues have open chain structure. The values of velocity constants depend on R-groups and is in the order: $COOEt > CH_3 > C_2H_5 > C_3H_7$. The high value due to $COOEt$ is due to its negativity. The velocity constant for acetylbenzoylacetone, which contains one positive and one negative group, is intermediate between the negative $COOEt$ group and the positive groups, CH_3 , C_2H_5 and C_3H_7 .

In Part I of this paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 60) the authors have studied the velocity of transformation of acetonedioxalic ester into chelidonic ester with a view to investigating the structure of 1 : 3 : 5-triketones and obtained an unimolecular constant. The change is